

Existence of Hazard on Persistence of Plastic: A Study of Edward Abbey's *Desert Solitaire: A Season in the Wilderness*

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Abstract:

Environment is getting degraded at an alarming rate in the twenty first century, which leads to various issues like climate change, global warming, and el-Niño. There could be cited a number of means that cause environmental deterioration wherein plastic plays such a crucial role. About 430 million tons of plastics are produced every year, 2:3 of which i.e. 280 million tons of plastics are disposable plastic items which no sooner turn into waste. The plastic wastes unlike others last for centuries together sans decomposing and vehemently harm the nature as well. A significant portion of plastic wastes end up year on year at water bodies like river, lake, and ocean that disturb the marine bio-diversity. Plastic remains to be one of the most pernicious things to the nature. Hence, the present study concentrates on how plastic became indispensable part of human life, what are the possible ways through which plastics endanger the living species on earth, and systematic changes to curb the use of plastics with restriction to Abbey's *Desert Solitaire: A Season in the Wilderness*.

Key Words: Plastic wastes, Perilous effect of plastic, Environmental degradation, Plastic to be ubiquitous, and Preventive measures.

Introduction:

Literature reflects various events which take place in an epoch with literariness and it varies as different age represents different thoughts and events. A piece of writing registers incidents and accidents occurred in a particular land, which forms the literature of the respective land such as Indian literature, African literature, British literature, Australian literature, Canadian literature and so on. In this regard, American literature concentrates on

the people, culture, development, environment, etc. of the United States of America. The American Literature evolved over the period of time in accordance with the change of period from classism to Post-modernism. It reflected the change in the standard of living, culture, and tradition of the people according to the age. There are various disciplines in the American literature like fiction, non-fiction, memoir, etc. which constrains vastness of literature into segments. However, all the discipline would deal with all the issues with their own unique style of narration. They could be categorised altogether into abroad section studies. For instance, the literature which deals with social movement and culture of the region would be approached with the literary lens of cultural studies.

The literature which delineates with environmental issues falls under the broad category called environmental studies. Eco-criticism is an approach to study the nexus between literature and environment. The term was used at the outset by William Rueckert, a literary scholar, in his essay entitled “Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism, which was published in 1978. He explicated that it is the study of literature by applying ecological principles. A researcher named Cheryl Glotfelty started offering lectures on ecocriticism at literary conferences since 1989. It resorted to the establishment of an organization called “The Association for the Literature and Environment (ASLE)” at Western Literature Association Conference which held in the United States of America in 1992. In 1996, Glotfelty defined the term ecocriticism as a “study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment”. It ultimately derived the scholars and writers to concentrate much on environmental issues, sustainable development, and the intervention of human beings into the harmony of nature, and environment in the beginning of the twenty-first century.

Edward Paul Abbey was a late-twentieth century writer, who was born on 29 January, 1927 in Pennsylvania, the United States. He was such a radical environmentalist. For

instance, he used to assert that ants are more harmful than the scorpion because no vegetation could be found for about ten meters surrounding the anthill as it mutilates everything. He is against to whatever seems to be against to nature. Such a radical environmentalist he was. His writings like *Desert Solitaire: A Season in the Wilderness*, *Monkey Wrench Gang*, *Hayduke Lives!* and *Fire on the Mountain* prominently focus on environmental sabotage. Abbey had not abstained from castigating the people who inflicted damage upon the country which he loved. He remained to be the man of the house to many environmentalists as he spared nothing which vehemently contributed to environmental degradation.

The present study concentrates on how plastic turns out to be the destructive force against environment through Abbey's *Desert Solitaire: A Season in the Wilderness*. *Desert Solitaire* is a non-fictional work which accounts the personal experience of Abbey in the American West. He asserts that plastic makes its presence in the natural places through various means which endangers the environment. In order to carry out the research, ecocentric theory is used. As far as ecocentrism is concerned, all the living and non-living components of ecosystem have their own innate value; human beings are one among them.

It is hard to find a place where no plastic could be witnessed. It takes on the harmony of the natural world with its maliciousness. So, the study attempts to answer the research questions like how plastic sets its foot everywhere?, how it harms the environment?, and how to do away with the plastic?

Review of Literature:

Zeenat Taher and Pratiti Nayak in their article entitled *Save the Creation: An Anguished Cry of a Man Depicted in Desert Solitaire: A Season in the Wilderness by Edward Abbey* analyse the text on various perspectives such as environmental perspective, social perspective, and economical perspective and state that *Desert Solitaire* deals prominently

with an intricate connection between nature and manmade things. Abbey deprecates industrial tourism citing its harmful effect on wilderness and also he advocates restricting humans' influx into wilderness areas in order to conserve the places. The authors express that preserving natural places intact sans degradation relays on economic as well.

John S. Farnsworth in his article entitled *What Does the Desert Say?: A Rhetorical Analysis of "Desert Solitaire"* states that the character of *Desert Solitaire* named Abbey has been an excellent replica of author Edward Abbey. The work has been a reflection of various events encountered or experienced for two summer seasons in Arches National Monument as a seasonal park ranger. However, it was no longer the only place where he said to have composed the book. Abbey stated in an interview that he wanted to be a novelist by writing fiction but he ended up with non-fiction *Desert Solitaire* as it seemed easy on account of merely copying out the journals that he had, but he did not do so completely as he missed out certain portions. Readers could not find a trace of Abbey's family anywhere in the book but in the journal VIII, Abbey has recorded that he became father and about Rita whom he loves.

Dr. J. Vignesious Stanley, et al in their article entitled *Contextualizing Environmental Vision of American Wilderness in Edward Abbey's Desert Solitaire* assert that Abbey was dissatisfied about southwest region to become interested to people and about unnecessary destruction of nature. He wishes to abandon civilisation. He says that he considers the desert as a face of God, and it's a duty of politicians to protect it. Desert does not care about human beings; it is so hostile but still Abbey considers it his heaven. The authors of the article argue that *Desert Solitaire* explicates the desire of human beings to enjoy everything sans hardship. Humans must have relationship with nature and furnish back what is taken from it.

Discussion and Finding:

In the twenty first century, environmental degradation turns out to be one of the prominent and serious concerns of the globe. Environmental issues cannot be confined within a country as none could set up a boundary to nature. If trees, for instance, are cut large in number in a country or natural resources are exploited, it would not only affect the respective nation but the whole world because nature is transcendental. Even the developed country like the United States of America is also struggling to prevent the environment from degrading further on account of scientific advancement and its demand for natural resources. The exponential growth of technology has shown human beings a comfortable means of living life by getting them accessed to electricity, internet, infrastructural development, transportation, and so on. People who enjoy the advancement of science failed to realize that they have to compromise with nature to get the things which make them lead such sophisticated lives. Natural resources like minerals, rare earth elements, coal, oil, gases, etc. are being exploited at an alarming rate. Though some financially as well as technologically dominant countries stop permitting the projects which exploit more natural resources as an initiative to control the damage, they carry out the same project in other less influential countries. The environment is getting degraded on various causes, but one of the undermined primary causes is dumping plastic.

Plastic was invented by Alexander Parkes in 1862, and he named it as Parkesine, but a real synthetic plastic was invented in 1907 by a Belgian- American chemist Leo Baekeland, and it was named as Bakelite. An indisputable positivity of plastic was that it would be unimpaired for long. The production of plastic in America was significantly escalated to 300% more during the period of II World War; it continued even after the war. The plastic replaced almost everything like steel in the car, paper for packaging, and the like. In the period of 1960s, plastic wastes had been noticed in the ocean for the first time; preceding it

people of America became aware of the possible environmental threat due to plastic. Anxiety on plastic wastes was spiralled during 1980 as most of the plastic products are disposable and it lasts forever in the environment. In order to make plastics more durable, flexible, and transparent, a chemical substance called Phthalates would be added while manufacturing. Besides, scientist had raised a warning that plastic may leach out the chemical substance into the thing which is packaged with like food and water, and it augmented fear of future with plastic. In an attempt to alleviate the rising tension, recycling method was adopted but it was not as effective as expected. In the twenty first century plastic has become ubiquitous; it could be found almost everywhere and in everything. Even breast milk contains micro-plastics. A study conducted in 2022 with thirty four healthy mothers by testing their breast milk a week after giving birth to babies revealed the shocking truth to the world that 75% of the sample was found with micro-plastics; it would be transmitted to newborn baby.

Plastic production is constantly spiralling year on year despite knowing its toxicity for environment on account of its inexpensiveness and portable with least weight. The plastic which had been manufactured in the entire 20th century was produced in the first decade of the twenty first century due to the ever growing demand. It seems almost impossible to live sans plastic at present because well-nigh all the things which make us lead a sophisticated life are made of plastics such as mobiles, computers, toothbrush, razor, cosmetics, and so on. Most of them are disposable; in other words, it can be used only once like plastic used for packaging. After using all of them turn out to be plastic wastes.

Tens of thousands tons of plastic wastes are being dumped on the land and water bodies throughout the years. It poses a serious threat to environment as well as human beings. When it is piled on the land, the plastic discharges harmful chemicals into soil and it filtrates into ground water. The living species that drink the water and that ingest flora which grow in the soil would be diagnosed with various health issues. Plastic takes at least hundred to

thousand or more years to be decomposed. When microorganism attempts to biodegrade the plastic waste, it emanates Methane (CH₄), a greenhouse gas. The organization of Economic Corporation and Development announced in 2019 that 3.4% of global greenhouse gas was emitted from plastic wastes and it reported that the percentage would be doubled in 2060 unless human beings control using the plastic. Greenhouse gas extensively contributes to the global warming, and it ultimately results in climate change. More or less 79% of plastic wastes are land filled. Certain landfills are equipped with the technology to convert the methane into energy, but not all the landfills are with such facility.

Plastic waste in ocean is on the other hand; it was estimated 165 million tons of plastic wastes to be in the ocean in 2012. Sea animals are facing a number of issues on account of the plastic wastes. Turtle like animals have been found with large amount of plastic on their stomach. It gradually leads them to perish as the plastic blockade their digestive system. Besides, these animals get entangled into abandoned fishing nets; it curbs their motion. Eventually, they die without food. Due to marine pollution, around 4,00,000 sea animals are died annually. Moreover, plastic waste leaches out chemicals into water which also shatters the marine eco-system significantly.

Edward Abbey's *Desert Solitaire: A season in the Wilderness* (1968) states that plastic is disseminated everywhere even in the place which is hard for human beings to get into. It was his first non-fictional work, and he became well known author after its publication. He worked as a park ranger in National Arches Monument, Utah, America from 1956 to 1957. The park received very least number of tourists about three thousand per year since the park had not had any amenities like road and toilet. However, a group of government officials approached Abbey on an evening and said to him that it was decided to lay out road inside the arches to attract more tourists to the park. The system of National park

was initiated to protect natural places but in order to generate more fortune, the road was laid inside which resulted in significant growth in advent of people to the park.

As I type these words, several years after the little episode of the gray jeep and the thirsty engineers, all that was foretold has come to pass. Arches National Monument has been developed. The Master plan has been fulfilled. Where once a few adventurous people came on weekends to camp for a night or two and enjoy a taste of the primitive and remote, you will now find serpentine streams of baroque automobiles pouring in and out, all through the spring and summer, in numbers that would have seemed fantastic when I worked there: from 3,000 to 30,000 to 300,000 per year [. . .]. (DS 54)

If a place starts receiving more number of visitors, other industries like food industries would also be set up to assist the them with what they want such as water, beverages, and processed food. Since plastic is weightless and more convenient as well for packaging, it has been used for the purpose. Tourists buy them and throw the plastic wrappers and empty bottles wherever they go whether it is forest or sea. Accumulation of plastic in both ocean and land is getting increased year on year wherein tourism turns out to be one of the indispensable causes. It was reported in BBC news on 27th November, 2019 that a 10-year old dead deer in the Khun Sathan National park, Thailand was found with about 7kg plastics inside its stomach. The officials of the park said that the deer should have been eating plastic for long. Incident of such kind is not limited; a young whale in Philippines was found dead with 88 pounds of plastic in its stomach. There is almost no place in the world where plastic could no longer be cited on account of human beings made it as one of the indispensable things in their lives.

Edward Abbey had taken up a trip in the Glen Canyon River along with his friend named Newcomb; the river was once explored by John Wesley Powel in 1869, and he called it as a land of beauty and glory. They were rafting in two respective rubber boats and enjoyed the beauty of the nature for days, but when they reached the spot where Glen Canyon dam was under construction, what they had witnessed startled Abbey. It was ecologically harmonious place until they see plastics, beer bottles, and cigarette buds floating on the water, where tourists were thronging.

Where he and his brave men once lined the rapids and glided through silent canyons two thousand feet deep the motorboats now smoke and whine, scumming the water with cigarette butts, beer cans and oil, dragging the water skiers on their endless rounds, clockwise. (DS 188)

The present environmental degradation has disproven almost all the earlier predictions how it would likely to be in 2026 by exceeding impairment. It is an ultimate result of humans' greed and urge to lead a sophisticated life. In this scientifically advanced world, of course, it is not possible to live without mobile, computer, vehicles, electricity, and the like; whereas they could not be accessed without compromising with natural resources. So, it is need of the hour to be resorted to sustainable development. Plastic is found everywhere even in the place where people do not reside. Prohibition of plastic is quite impossible, but its usage can be curbed especially disposable plastic like carry bags. Plastic wastes could vehemently be controlled if people begin avoiding disposable plastic and reuse them. However, all the plastic products could not be reused as their quality changes based on their grade. There are seven types of plastics such as PET, HDPE, PVC, LDPE, PP, PS, and Other Plastic.

'Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)' is known as wrinkle-free fibre. It could be used to pack the food and beverages. It prevents oxygen from entering in and spoiling the edible item

which is packed with plastic as well as prevents Carbon dioxide from leaving the carbonated soft drinks. The longer plastic of its kind contains edible items, the more it emanates “antimony trioxide” which causes cancer. ‘High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE)’ is stronger than that of PET. It is used to contain juice, shampoo, and so on. It is believed to be better option for food and drink, but it also leaches out “estrogens mimicking additive chemicals” which disturb hormonal system of human beings. ‘Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC)’ is the second most demanded plastic and also equally perilous in the world. It releases various chemicals such as Phthalates, dioxins, cadmium, and so on, which cause cancer and it cannot be recycled whatsoever. ‘Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE)’ is a plastic which is widely used in the world. It is quite hard to be recycled and it makes changes in humans’ hormone. ‘Polypropylene Plastic (PP)’ is considered to be better material for packing hot food. Feeding bottle is also made of this plastic, but it cannot be recycled entirely. ‘Polystyrene (PS)’ is used to make products such as egg carton, disposable cups, helmets, etc. If it is exposed to heat, it releases styrene which affects humans’ brain and nerves system. Besides, it is with low recycling rate. The plastic which is not categorized among these six is considered to be the ‘other Plastic.’ Polycarbonate (PC) is a common plastic used in this category. It causes multiple problems like damaging chromosome in ovaries, reducing sperm count, coming of an age early, impairing brain, cardio, and neurology system, obesity, diabetes, cancer, infertility, etc. Many countries have banned this type of plastic and it has the least recycling rate.

There is no plastic which could be asserted to be 100% safe and will not harm environment and human beings. Since it became indispensable and also essential for certain things, severe action must be taken to control the plastic production; for which people should be advised to use the plastic which is reusable and recyclable. Unfortunately only 14% of the total production of packaging plastic is recycled. So, awareness about plastic wastes should

be created among people. On the other hand, government should also make policy change in order to plummet the plastic usage. As a part of this drive, many established shops and supermarkets begun charging for issuing bag which prevents people slightly from getting the plastic. Tamil Nadu, a state in south India, has initiated campaign in 2022 to encourage the people of state to use cotton bags instead of plastic bags in the view of curbing the plastic usage. Saradha U in her article entitled *Manjappai and its Tamil roots: How the yellow bag has long been part of TN households* on The News Minute magazine mentioned “After Tamil Nadu chief minister MK Stalin launched the ‘Meendum Manjapai Vizhipunarvu Iyakkam’ campaign in December to encourage the people to quit using plastic bags and revive the usage of the traditional yellow bags . . . as it promotes sustainability.”

Instead of depending upon recycling and land filling to cope with the negative impact of the plastic such as health issue and environmental degradation, other alternative is needed to be invented to uproot the plastic entirely from the planet. In this regard, many researches were carried out across the globe to find alternative means. Plastic will never leave the earth without leaving an equal destruction to environment unless it is biodegraded. Hence, it is proposed to use 1% Oxo-biodegradable (OBD) additive while manufacturing the plastic materials. It had been said that plastic with the OBD additive would be biodegraded after a period of time. This method has already been adopted in various countries. Obbe S.B and Adamu A.A in their article entitled *Plastic Pollution: Causes, Effects, and Preventions* states that “A number of countries in Europe, Latin America, South Asia, Middle East and Africa are already using OBD in tackling the menace of plastics that have escaped the collection and therefore pollutions the environment (85-95).” It was also tested and was found that plastic added with the additive would be degradable both on land and in water. As Edward Abbey penned in *Desert Solitaire: A Season in the Wilderness*, plastic wastes are found even in the places which are ecologically rich where humans intervention is limited. If it is not paid

attention right away, it will lead to irrecoverable loss of bio-diversity.

Conclusion:

Environmental degradation is one of the major concerns of the world in this scientifically advanced epoch. Despite being affected by various causes, plastic holds a significant position in harming the nature. As plastic is flexible as well as with meagre weight, its usage is being spiralled across the world. On the other hand, most of the plastic products are disposable so its waste is also equally hiked. Plastic cannot be biodegraded like other materials; it takes about hundred to thousand or more years to be degraded. In the meanwhile, it pollutes the place wherever it is whether on land or in water. If plastic is on land, it leaches out harmful chemicals which contaminate ground water; whatever the living species that drink the water get affected. When micro-organisms on the soil attempts to degrade them, plastic emanates a gas called Methane which drives to climate change. On the other hand, the plastic in the ocean causes death of various sea animals on multiple grounds and leads to marine biodiversity loss. Such a harmful plastic is found almost everywhere, for which tourism is also contributing significantly. It has been explicated vividly in *Desert Solitaire: A Season in the wilderness* by Edward Abbey.

Abbey states that tourism is converted into industrial tourism in order to generate more revenue to the government. In view of getting more tourists, governments started providing many amenities such as road and toilet inside the natural places. As tourists influx is increased, industries like food court which sells water, beverages, chocolates, etc. had also been set up. Most of the items sold in the shops are packaged with plastic. That is how plastic entered the place where human beings are not whatsoever residing. Plastic which is used by human beings harms not only others living species on the planet but also them because micro plastic is found even in the breast milk which is said to be pure once. Plastic products are

categorized into seven types based on its quality and harmfulness but to say in general all the materials made of plastic are harmful to both humans and to environment.

As plastic became almost indispensable at present, preventive measures are needed to be taken right away. Plastic could be found on everything such as pen, cosmetic items, etc. So, it cannot be avoided entirely but be curbed. First of all awareness must be created among people about plastic pollution to make them control using plastic. Instead of leaving everything on people's hands, government should also take some measures to make people prevent using plastic like "meendum manjapai" scheme initiated in Tamil Nadu, India. It is said that only 14% of packaging plastic is recycled. So, recycling rate should also be escalated. Instead of depending upon the process of recycling much, measure like inclusion of 1% Oxo-biodegradable additive in plastic products to make them bio-degradable after certain period of time.

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